

THE VALUE OF USING THE FAMILY ENVIRONMENT AND TRADITIONS ON PERSONAL SPIRITUALITY

RAHMONOVA ZAMIRAKHAN YAKUBJANOVNA

SENIOR LECTURER OF GENERAL PEDAGOGICAL DEPARTMENT OF ADU

Annotatsiya:

National traditions and values build a spiritually healthy family. Where healthy nationalism flourishes, the appreciation of universal virtues increases, friendly relations between nations also develop, and it is important to raise selfless people who are loyal to their people, country, and serve for the development of the nation and the homeland.

Key words: beautiful, honor, dignity, spiritual and moral, family, crooked intention, traditions, loyalty, mutual, love.

Keeping national values firmly in one's heart, making the environment, nature and life beautiful and prosperous, the foundations of democracy and advanced ideas practiced in society are considered great values in the society. A person's value can be his first respect and attitude towards himself and this society, he can regulate his behavior, he can increase his self-requirement and control.

A person's self-respect allows him to maintain his honor and reputation. And this is the process that comes to him through the realization of his national identity. The personal dignity of a person is one of the social characteristics arising from national values, and it is a noble force that takes him to the top. In this respect, values are a great resource that ensures social freedom and spiritual purity of a person. The improvement of his useful and effective aspects for himself and those around him improves not only himself, but also the spiritual and moral qualities of those around him. For this reason, in the requirements of the development of the society, the value of a person has a social meaning as it comes from national values, which are formed as a result of a person's education, training and daily work.

The effective use of the influence of national values in family upbringing is related to the opportunity created by society for this family and the level of social protection of this family, which can be observed in the following directions:

- o social protection of the family.
- o protection of children in the family and society;
- o educational support.

Human value has a social essence in terms of its origin from national values, which are formed as a result of a person's education, training and daily work. As a result of the restoration of national values in the years of independence, a wide path was opened to restore human dignity, increase his knowledge, cultural level, and develop his internal skills. During the last decades, a lot of work has been done to protect the human person, his rights, freedoms and dignity. The most important of these are activities aimed at strengthening family and school cooperation and increasing its effectiveness.

In our country, social protection of family, motherhood and childhood is one of the priority directions of our state policy, and it includes the following main directions:

- improvement of the legal foundations of family relations, ensuring legal protection of family interests, protection of motherhood and childhood rights;
- creating conditions for ensuring the social interests of the family, improving the conditions for protecting the health of family members and raising the level of education;
- creating conditions for ensuring the economic interests of the family, increasing the income of the family, the level of employment of family members, improving livelihood and living conditions, providing state support to low-income families;
- creating conditions for improving the moral and moral foundations and cultural interests of the family;
- increasing the role of the family in raising a healthy, intelligent young generation, improving the tasks of the family and society in raising a mature generation in all respects;
- scientific and social research of family problems, collection and improvement of statistical reports showing economic and social condition of family, women and children.

In fact, formation of legal literacy and moral culture of family members; deciding on a healthy lifestyle in all aspects; achieving social and economic stability and well-being of the family; widening of entrepreneurship in the family; determining measures to prevent various forms of disability; raising a perfect person in the family; to strengthen the cooperation of official state and public organizations dealing with family issues, family, neighborhood, school and community under the basis of creation and implementation of the system of preparing young people for independent life in common humanitarian and national values; At the heart of creating a healthy psychological environment in the family, such issues as crime, annulment of marriage, drug addiction, unhealthy beliefs, domestic uncleanness, and the prevention of various forms of immorality are the basis for the formation of families at the level of society's requirements. The process of building a just, legal, democratic society in our country under the conditions of ensuring the priority of the law, the formation of the legal culture of family members has become one of the priority directions for ensuring the interests of the family.

As a result of the negative impact of the traditions of foreign cultures on the minds, worldviews and consciousness of our people, which are contrary to our people's ideas about morality, attitude, shame, honesty and purity, and human dignity, some negative points have appeared. National traditions and values build a spiritually healthy family. is enough. Where healthy nationalism flourishes, the appreciation of universal virtues increases, and friendly relations between nations develop. Such national values and traditions play an important role in the establishment of a strong family and in educating future children in the world as selfless people who are loyal to their people, country, and serve for the development of the nation and homeland.

Raising a spiritually and physically mature generation is not only a national need, but also a matter of national importance - it is a noble goal for all brotherly peoples born and raised in our multi-ethnic Motherland. In the process of enriching the heredity of our people, raising a mentally and physically healthy generation, a perfect human personality is formed - a man of the 21st century, who is a joint member of the family, state and society. According to historians, Sahibgiron wanted his children to have three qualities. First of all, humanity, then observation, and finally, the consequence - tyranny. In order to find out what qualities our grandfather's children and descendants wished to have, let's first look at "Temur's Laws". In its first pages, one can read such an opinion: "One who is built in my experience, a businessman, possessor of courage and enthusiasm, determined, entrepreneurial and vigilant, is better than thousands and thousands of inactive and indifferent people." I think that this wisdom embodied our grandfather's understanding of a healthy and perfect human being, that is, his

observation that only a person with mature human qualities and characteristics can be the backbone of the country. In another place, Sahibqiran states that a person who has "perseverance, patience, health and vigilance, diligence and enthusiasm" is capable of doing any hard work.

It is natural that every citizen who has studied the history of views on education in Central Asia will not only increase his level of knowledge and outlook, but also realize his identity and become a true patriot.

Right now, there is a lot of attention being paid to neighborhoods. In the neighborhood, everyone knows each other, they live together. We all know the influence of old elders and wise people on young people. there are people in every neighborhood without whom neither a wedding nor a party is complete.

We will witness such events. even the neighbors who are quarreling or disagreeing, when it is said that "brother so-and-so is coming" or "brother so-and-so should be called" will automatically shut up. In this sense, it should be noted that the percentage of elderly parents in the family is incomparable. Is it possible that we cannot oppose the spirituality of our grandfathers and heavenly mothers to the deviant intentions and verbless verbs? yes, we can resist. This can be affected by the attitude of the community, neighborhood, and people. Because the community cursed man has never had a green garden. The debt of Uzbek manners, Uzbek humanity is also measured by this community and the mood and attitude of the majority.

Our wonderful national traditions invite people to solidarity, brotherhood and sincerity. It was not recognized that customs and habits formed in the minds of generations over the centuries cannot be lost with one blow. Any attempt to inculcate the learned Udum into the masses will be counter-productive unless there is a more advanced, more natural and modern spiritual need for them.

Our paintings have been enriched and changed due to national development and spiritual growth. The soul of a nation is in its morals. That's why every nation is passionate about its traditions and human qualities. Even when the nation is in the most dire straits, it does not take its spirituality to the market, it does not make a living by selling its honor and violating its conscience.

Bringing up the young generation in the family on the basis of family traditions, genealogy, profession, moral and spiritual values by the example of parents, preparing them for family life by forming loyalty to the family, mutual love and respect in their minds will give the expected result. For this purpose, in order to prepare parents for

the process of upbringing, it is appropriate to restore and improve the work of parents' universities, to include the course "Preparation of young people in family life" in the content of general education schools, higher and secondary special education. Publication of booklets from the "Family Library" series and the special "Family" magazine, which provide methodical support to parents in family education, and the introduction of the "Family Psychology and Pedagogy" course to higher and secondary special educational institutions of all directions is a means of turning the family into an exemplary place of education.

It is natural that our young men and women who are coming of age are satisfied with the education and reforms being carried out.

development of educational forms, methods and tools in accordance with the requirements of the world model;

o equipping educational, cultural and educational institutions based on new modern techniques and technology;

The Uzbek people have paid special attention to family spirituality since ancient times. Today, it is the sacred duty of every family to raise young people who meet the requirements of our independent republic using the spiritual heritage.

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